

AUDIT BOX: VEHICLE ASSESSMENT AND JAMMING ATTACK DETECTION IN CCAM ENVIRONMENTS

Manel Rodríguez Recasens

Automotive Cybersecurity Engineer, Applus IDIADA

Tarragona, Spain

manel.rodriguez@idiada.com

Victor Jimenez

IT&OT Security Researcher, Eurecat, Centre Tecnològic de Catalunya

Barcelona, Spain

victor.jimenez@eurecat.org

ABSTRACT

The connected world is in constant growth, and a proof of it is the automotive world and smart cities environment. It is a fact that the urban streets are evolving to a more intelligent and connected scenario. This concept comes along with a lot of advantages, but it also brings the opportunity to bad actors to perform attacks to these environments. This paper aims to explain what envisions our tool called Audit Box, which is developed by Applus IDIADA and EURECAT and pretends to audit the vehicles while they are circulating in a smart city informing to the Vehicle Security Operations Center (VSOC) (or corresponding OEM or Traffic Management Center) if a vulnerability or jamming situation has been encountered. The Audit Box is one of the technologies developed in a European project from the Horizon Europe programme called SELFY, which is a toolbox and is devoted to address continuous assessments of the robustness and resilience of CCAM solutions versus cyberattacks, malfunctions, misuses, or failures of the systems. The specific technology described in this paper, the Audit Box, interacts with the rest of the SELFY's tools to provide a SELF-assessment and robustness to the CCAM environment.

INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

The cities are no longer what they used to be, they have been evolving being smarter and more efficient. The numbers are clear, and it is also certain that they will continue to the same direction.

As it can be seen in figure 1 which information has been extracted from a recent study of Precedence Research [1] the expected global smart cities market size, in 2022 was estimated at US\$ 1273,15 billion and it is expected to get by 2030 to US\$ 7162,5 billion.

Figure 1 - Smart cities market size

This trend is because one of the most important actors in a city (the vehicles) are changing as increasing their connectivity, thus existing a synergy between both worlds.

Nowadays, vehicles are capable to interact with the environment having multiple external connections. A very basic example is that a big percentage of the vehicles have a Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) integrated which provides navigation facilities to the driver to easily get to its destination. However, there are many other examples of connectivity with the exterior (WiFi, Bluetooth (BT), cellular connectivity...) and if we go to a further step, the autonomous vehicles will base its functionality on its inputs through the sensors, cameras or thanks to the Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) messages received from other vehicles and infrastructure incrementing the attack surface and bringing dangerous scenarios in case of failure or cyber-attack.

The more connections a vehicle has, the more attack's surface exists, and is for this reason that every possibility of threat exploitation must be tackled to avoid future damages.

The Audit Box pretends to cover these possible dangerous scenarios increasing the robustness of the CCAM's ecosystem by increasing the detection of vulnerabilities and jamming situations by continuously evaluating the vehicle networks.

This paper aims to explain its concept and its target as it is a tool still in the definition phase and will be implemented in the following months by Applus IDIADA and EURECAT.

STATE OF THE ART

The idea of auditing the vehicles is not new. In fact, the CCAM association, in the SRIA [2] (Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda) defines topics for research related to CCAM. In cluster 5 (Key Enabling Technologies) it is described the need for Robustness and resilience, and it mentions literally that threats, failures, problems, and malicious interactions will have to be detected in real-time and fed to a decision-making process on response actions. They suggest that a tool suite is appropriate to perform these actions. Some European Projects have already worked in this concept. For instance, the project CARMEL [3] aims to introduce an anti-hacking intrusion detection/prevention system in the automotive industry. In this case, they suggest to introduce a device integrated in the vehicle to perform intrusion detection system (IDS) using pre-trained machine learning models that detect anomalies on the sensor data collected which may point to malicious attacks.

Other scientific publications have been working with the idea of vehicle diagnosis using trusted platform measurements [4] and with methods for risk assessment in a Smart City considering VANETs [5]. In this publication [6], the authors present the CVGuard system which proposed a cloud-edge architecture with the Road Side Unit (RSU) analyzing V2X traffic to detect attacks based on IDS/IPS systems. However, does not analyze WiFi or BT surfaces neither jamming attacks.

Regarding jamming detection, there are many studies in the literature. Some of them are mostly focused in VANETS. This publication [7] proposes a method to jointly detect global positioning system (GPS) spoofing and jamming attacks in a V2X network and in this publication [8] the authors focus on hybrid jamming detection strategy in terms of node centric misbehavior detection in VANET.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to present a distributed audit system attached to the RSUs and using a cloud/edge/vehicle infrastructure with the aim to audit the complete fleet of vehicles in a region or smart city by exploring and searching vulnerabilities and

It is necessary to understand that nowadays the vehicles can be compared to a house with wheels. Considering the amount of information that can be sent through its communication channels, it is as important as it is at a private home network to increase the security features to avoid unauthorized parties accessing the network and eavesdrop the data sent by its internal devices (also personal devices), increasing the privacy and security reducing a hypothetical damage scenario.

A state-of-the-art analysis will be performed during the development of the Audit Box in order to find which vulnerabilities can be detected from each network and which ones are feasible to be audited by the Audit Box. As an example, considering previous investigations on the WiFi vector, the following threats and damages scenarios have been already identified:

- Credentials theft: A bad practice followed by a percentage of the population is to use the same password in different services. So, there could be the situation where an attacker gets access to other accounts thanks to stealing the one used in its vehicle.
- Data theft: Sniff data sent by the devices inside the network.
- Remote access to other devices: With the possibility of entering to the network it also exists the possibility, usually low, to access to other devices. The worst case would be granting access to the CAN bus.

This is just a short list of possible threats to be considered in a WiFi network, but the goal is to explore more interfaces and their related threats and vulnerabilities.

So, the Audit Box covers two main functionalities, vehicle audit (which will inform about possible vehicle network vulnerabilities) and jamming detection on a delimited region (which wants to prevent an incorrect system behavior).

VEHICLE AUDIT

From the vehicle audit perspective and from the possible vehicle networks, the Audit Box will be focused mainly on WiFi and Bluetooth. The reason is that these specific networks are very common in vehicles, and from an inspection point of view are the ones which are more feasible to be attacked and therefore extract more information and detect possible vulnerabilities, as previously explained. When the Audit Box detects any of these two interfaces, a battery of tests will be executed on one or both. The tests can be configured to be incremental by accessing deeper layers at each iteration.

A graphical example of a possible approach can be seen in the following image:

Figure 3 - Example of an audit

As can be appreciated in figure 3, depending on how deep the Audit Box will be able to go in each vehicle network, more information about the existing vulnerabilities will be extracted.

The Audit Box will get conclusions on vulnerabilities which can lead to an attack and perform an audit report.

Once the audit of a specific vehicle has been performed because it was requested by the backend (VSOC), an audit report will be sent and saved inside the Audit Box for future information queries.

In a distributed architecture of vehicles, RSUs and cloud, this information collected on each of the RSUs of a smart city provides a big picture to a VSOC or Traffic Management Center of the security status of the fleet of vehicles and regions of the smart city and therefore it provides enriched information to response adequately to each detected situation. (For instance, trigger safety actions in a region of the city where there is a jamming situation or inform users of a

specific vehicle's model to update their system to fix a vulnerability.

JAMMING ALARM

The second target of the Audit Box is to detect if a surrounded area is being affected by a jamming attack. The reason to detect and inform about this type of attacks is to be aware of which communication channels are not reliable at this moment, and inform a control entity (VSOC, Traffic Management Center) of this situation by means of another channel.

This kind of detection can be detected at any region at any time a possible jamming attack, providing information to the response tools to act properly.

TECHNICAL CHALLENGES DURING THE IMPLEMENTATION

During the concept and implementation phase of the audit box some technical and operational challenges have been encountered.

From one side, technical barriers related to the industrialization of the product (size, cost, integration...) have been considered. In order to audit a complete city and its fleet of vehicles it is required to deploy as many Audit Boxes as RSUs. Due to this fact, an important requirement during the design and implementation phase is to minimize as much as possible the cost of the final product without reducing its performance. Therefore, the selection of the hardware devices (by doing a state-of-the-art and benchmarking) it's being crucial, not only because of its cost but also of its size and means of integration as it will be attached to an RSU and it is envisioned to be a very low intrusive solution in the road environment.

Another important point is that it is required that the vehicles are not circulating at high velocity. Ideally, they are stopped because of a traffic light or traffic congestion. Nevertheless, the Audit Box should be able to perform the audit scans as fast as possible. Two types of scans are foreseen (fast scan or deep scan) adapting it to each situation.

An addition challenge (technical and operational) that the Audit Box needs to face is one of the most important topics nowadays, which is the data protection of the vehicle and its users. During the Audit process, the results have to be linked to a vehicle identifier and be sent to the

corresponding VSOC or OEM. If a malicious actor can eavesdrop this communication or grants access to the internal storage of the Audit Box/VSOC, he/she could get access to private information about the vehicle's data (and user). Another kind of sensible information would be that the attacker discovers which are the vulnerabilities detected by the Audit Box to each kind of vehicle, being able to exploit them before a patch is applied. Because of these reasons, it has been required to put special attention to preserve the privacy of the users and protect communications and the database storage.

Finally, continuous auditing of the complete fleet of vehicles of a city can generate too much traffic. Therefore, an efficient and distributed database and synchronization algorithm has to be considered to avoid too much audit events to the same vehicle.

CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The Audit Box brings the opportunity to get updated security status of the vehicles' networks with no need to bring them to a technical service and is able to detect vulnerabilities (also zero-day attacks) on a vehicle or a fleet of vehicles. It also monitors and detects jamming attacks which could affect different smart city services. It provides to the control systems (VSOC, Traffic Management Center) an enriched security status of the CCAM environment in order they can respond adequately. The next step is to develop and implement the solution, evaluate its impact and its viability in the SELFY project and in future smart cities.

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